

‘We would also appreciate having Creole classes as well’: Private school parents’ attitudes towards the role of Kreol Seselwa in education

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Introduction

Private schools constitute a relatively large portion of the pre-, primary and secondary school sectors globally. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2020, p.159) data show that an average 18% of students in OECD countries were enrolled in private schools in 2018, and many of these schools apply English-only Medium of Instruction (EMI) policies. According to International School Community (ISC) Research (2022), 5.8 million children were enrolled in private EMI schools around the world in 2022. The sector is growing steadily. For example, the number of students enrolled in these types of schools has increased by 53% over the past ten years and the number of international EMI schools has increased by 60%, from 8,246 to 13,180 over the same period (ISC Research, 2022). According to Bailey (2015), the bulk of this increase is the result of wealthy *local*, as opposed to expatriate, parents increasingly choosing the private EMI school option for their children. Regardless, international EMI education today is a multi-billion-dollar industry, turning over an estimated 53.8 billion dollars annually (ibid.). This makes private EMI schools important players to consider in overall national educational policy.

The typically English-only policies of many private EMI schools have a huge impact on the linguistic and cultural identities of the children who attend these schools. But, equally important, are the language ideological standards that these schools set, and the impact these have on national language-in-education policy. In post-colonial contexts, many see private EMI schools as an example of ‘elite-closure’ in education, i.e. the setting up of barriers to entry for certain groups based on socioeconomic status, race, or gender, thereby perpetuating inequality and preserving the dominance of the elite class (Myers-Scotton, 1993). Language is a key factor in this structure of closure, inequality and dominance, and here English carries huge symbolic and pragmatic value. Based on results of a meta-study of research into the decisions of parents choosing international schools, MacKenzie (2010) lists ‘English’ as the primary factor. English-only policies are motivated as a way of preparing students for an increasingly globalized world, where English is seen as the lingua franca of business, science, and diplomacy. English is considered essential for success and confers a huge competitive advantage on the global job market.

The above arguments are echoed by various state institutions in the post-colonial world motivating the persistence of systems which exclude local languages from education. These so-called subtractive EMI approaches remain the norm in most of Sub-Saharan Africa

(SSA), but also in other parts of the world (Trudell, 2016, p.96). In most such systems, children are taught in a home/familiar language during the first two to four years of primary schooling, after which English is introduced as the sole medium of instruction. The negative outcomes of subtractive English-only models are well-documented. Children who do not understand what is being said in the classroom are effectively silenced, making learner-centered pedagogy based on interactive knowledge construction and exploratory talk difficult (e.g. Clegg, 2019). Textbooks designed for readers with native-like fluency of English become inaccessible to learners, and examinations fail to give indication of learners' understanding of the subject matter since they fail to communicate what they know in an unfamiliar language (ibid.). Aspects such as these lead to high drop-out rates and failures, especially among already vulnerable groups. In sum, monolingual EMI greatly exacerbates educational inequity and marginalizes indigenous languages' and cultures' role in academia (see, for example, Deutschmann & Zelime, 2021; Milligan et al., 2020).

Despite such evidence, EMI policies remain firmly rooted within the education systems in Sub-Saharan Africa (Clegg & Simpson, 2016, p.360). Reasons for this may of course vary, but there is generally great opposition for change towards more inclusive multilingual models among key stakeholders, such as parents and teachers (see, for example, Zelime & Deutschmann, 2018). Trudell et al. (2015) argue that the resistance to change is fuelled by various myths regarding language and education, and also by the examples set by international EMI schools, where the elite send their children. After all, why should parents accept education for their children in a local language which may exclude them from global opportunities, when the children of the elite receive all their education in English and have access to the world? In this way, standards set by private EMI schools become a factor that politicians and policy makers have to consider when formulating new policies.

There have been several calls for more educational research into the private EMI school sector given its importance and how it impacts on national educational policy (Bailey, 2021; Gardner-McTaggart, 2018; Kim & Mobrand, 2019;). For example, we need a better understanding of the language ideologies of the parents of children in these schools. Are the current English-only policies, adopted by many private EMI schools, really a reflection of the elite's attitudes, and an example of 'elite-closure', as suggested above; or is this yet another untried myth of language and education? In this paper we pursue this, and other questions related to the language ideologies of parents of private EMI-school pupils in Seychelles, a small post-colonial island nation in the Indian Ocean.

Aims and research questions

The overall aim of this study is to gain a better understanding of the language practices in the homes of private EMI school students and the language ideologies of the parents;

factors which all could play a significant role in shaping not only the language-in-education policies of private schools, but also of the public sector.

More specifically we ask the following questions:

- ◆ What are the family language ideologies in the homes of private school families?
- ◆ What languages are spoken at home?
- ◆ Are children discouraged/encouraged to speak Kreol Seselwa at home and why?
- ◆ How do parents view the importance of the three national languages of Seychelles in formal and informal written and spoken communication?
- ◆ What are parents' views on the role of Kreol Seselwa in education?

Theoretical framework - language and learning

Theoretically most modern language-in-education policies are largely guided by social constructivist learning perspectives (Vygotsky, 1978), i.e. a general belief that learning takes place in social interaction with others, and that language is an essential part of this process. Here, however, Halliday (2004) recognizes three ways of thinking about the relationship between learning and language: learning a language, learning through language, and learning about language. While all three of these aspects are relevant in educational contexts, they need to be kept apart. Learning English is not the same thing as learning through English or learning about English, for example.

How educational institutions think about and interpret the term 'language' and its role in education is central in multilingual educational contexts. Historically, there has been a strong tendency in educational policy and praxis to define language in terms of distinct and definable standard systems, guided by set rules, and conventions. This view has often come with underlying ideological assumptions of what is correct and incorrect language usage, prestige and value attached to certain languages (such as English), and a monolingual view of language of learning and teaching, where the mixing of languages is considered bad practice (Erling et al., 2017).

Another important aspect of language and learning that has greatly influenced language-in-education policies, especially in post-colonial contexts, is theories and methods related to language learning. *Immersion* is one such model. This model advocates total immersion in the second language with minimum interference of the first language as the best method for language learning (see Genesee (2013) for a more thorough discussion of different types of immersion). Although this approach emphasizes real-life communication and contextual learning over explicit instruction of grammar rules and vocabulary, the goal is native-like proficiency in 'correct' English. In an immersive language learning environment, learners are ideally exposed to the target language through activities such as conversations, reading materials, and media in that language. The goal is for learners to

develop their language skills naturally, similar to how they acquired their native language, by engaging in meaningful interactions and gradually internalizing linguistic patterns and structures. This is the model propagated by most international EMI schools, many of which have rules that even forbid children to speak languages other than English during breaks.

While immersion appears to be successful in developing high levels of L2 proficiency (Genesee, 2013), it comes at a cost. Learning *through* a second language is a challenge and something which risks hindering more general cognitive and linguistic development (Cummins, 2000). Furthermore, Baker (2011, p.72) argues that the demotion of local languages leads to negative social effects including ‘less positive self-concept, loss of cultural or ethnic identity, with possible alienation and marginalization’ (see also Deutschmann & Zelime, 2015). The exclusion of local languages from education directly or indirectly also risks leading to the exclusion of the local context from the learning process, especially when curricula, including learning materials and examinations, are based on foreign (often British) systems (Trudell, 2016; Zelime & Deutschmann, 2019).

Alternative pedagogic models that build on more fluid views of language are, however, emerging. Here attention is shifted away from language forms and standard languages, and emphasis is instead put on language as ‘meaning making’ and social practice. Familiar concepts include so-called ‘translanguaging’ (Garcia & Li, 2014), defined by Lin (2019, p.8) as ‘a fluid dynamic flow of meaning making’, and the African value system of *Ubuntu* ‘where languages are interwoven in a system of infinite dependent relations that recognize no boundaries between them’ (Makalela, 2019, p.238).

These theoretical shifts have in turn given rise to *flexible Multilingual Education* (MLE); additive multilingual approaches that validate and build on all the learners’ linguistic resources, including non-standard language forms and varieties (Erling et al., 2017, pp. 22–23). Several multilingual teaching and learning models have been proposed. Bonacina-Pugh et al. (2021, p.447) make a distinction between approaches based on ‘fluid languaging’, which draw on all the semiotic resources available in the classroom indiscriminately, and ‘fixed language approaches’, where the functions of the languages in the classroom are defined and more carefully planned. Cenoz & Gorter (2021, p.18) make a similar distinction between ‘spontaneous translanguaging’ and ‘pedagogical translanguaging’ (see also Probyn, 2015), where the latter is defined as ‘planned by the teacher’.

There is an ongoing debate on the merits and drawbacks of various approaches such as those described above. For example, Heugh & Stroud (2020, p.219) caution that fluid approaches risk neglecting the linguistic realities in many parts of SSA and the language practices students need to master in order to ‘access [...] the standardised variety of written and spoken languages that open doors to higher education and high-level employment opportunities’. This linguistic reality is important to bear in mind when discussing

language ideological issues in education, especially in relation to parents' attitudes. We can assume that most parents prioritize their children's future over ideological principles.

Previous research

There is a limited number of studies exploring the language ideologies of private school parents. Studies that do exist give a somewhat divided picture of attitudes and ideologies, which is hardly surprising given that these have been carried out in vastly diverse contexts.

The most comprehensive study in this field is a meta-study from 2010 conducted by MacKenzie. Based on sub-studies from five countries – Switzerland, Japan, Singapore, Argentina and Israel – encompassing a total of 831 respondents, MacKenzie could isolate eight recurring themes which were referred to when parents motivated their EMI school choice. Of these themes, four were directly related to English and the opportunities that the language affords globally (the factors: 'English', 'International education', 'College abroad' and 'International exams' – IGCSEs for example). The remaining factors ('Reputation', 'Class size', 'Affective factors', and 'Curriculum') were more general in nature. One common source of dissatisfaction recorded under the theme 'Curriculum' was that local state school curricula were too focused on the national context, and that parents considered it more important for their children to have a place in a globally minded society (Ezra, 2007).

Many of the themes identified by MacKenzie are also recurrent in more recent studies. In a study from 2016, based on the responses of 68 Saudi parents from private EMI schools, Al-Qahtani and Al Zumor found that Saudi parents held favorable attitudes towards the use of English Medium Instruction (EMI) since they recognized the importance of English as a global language that can offer enhanced future opportunities. Furthermore, the parents in the study believed that early total exposure to English as the medium of instruction was the most effective method of language acquisition (cf. immersion above). In a study from Bahrain involving 112 private school parents, Bailey (2021) could show that a majority of parents motivated their choice of school with reference to the advantages that English brought with it on the global market in terms of education and job opportunities. Similarly, Paulsrud and Cunningham (forthcoming) found that Swedish parents motivated their EMI school choice with a desire for the linguistic capital that EMI would offer.

In all the above studies, however, it appears that there is a conflict between the global and the local in the parents' expressions of the ideologies. Parents see EMI as partially problematic since it interferes with the development of local language and culture. Paulsrud and Cunningham (forthcoming) report on parents lamenting a loss of cultural capital when 'Swedish language is moved backstage' (p.6). In Al-Qahtani and Al Zumor's (2016) study, parents expressed concerns that the emphasis on English had a detrimental impact on their children's proficiency in Arabic. The response from one parent, 'my child

doesn't know many Arabic words which makes him feel embarrassed in front of his grandparents and the rest of the family' (p. 29), clearly illustrates the issue of loss of cultural identity discussed above (Baker, 2011). Similarly, Bailey's (2021) study revealed that many parents were seriously concerned over the loss of Arabic language, culture and identity that EMI resulted in, as illustrated by the following quote: 'I have friends who are fully Arabic, fully Bahraini, born and raised here, and their kids can't speak a word of Arabic. [...]. This is our mother tongue. I think there's a certain level of respect and pride to have in your own language.' (p.9).

With the risk of drawing too broad conclusions from limited research material, I tentatively hypothesize that there has been a slight shift in attitudes in the last decade towards more favourable views of multilingual language-in-education policies. It seems that parents in the above studies are motivated by the linguistic capital and global opportunities that come with English, but that they also appreciate the value of local languages and culture. They seem to desire global AND local linguistic and cultural proficiency for their children – a 'glocal' competence.

Language and education in Seychelles

Seychelles has three official languages: Kreol Seselwa, English and French. Somewhat simplified, one can say that Kreol Seselwa is the first language of the majority. According to the 2022 Census (National Bureau of Statistics, 2024), it is the first main language spoken at home by 85.1% of the population. English is the first language in the homes of 8% of the population and French by in a mere 0.5% of the households, according to the same report.

In Seychelles, French was the sole medium of instruction in education until the 1940s, when the church-owned schools were replaced by more formal and state organized arrangements based on the English system and language (Fleischmann 2008, p.74). During the entire colonial period, Kreol Seselwa, though used in everyday communication amongst much of the population, remained a low status language, and only existed in its spoken form. It was confined to informal discourse and completely banned from schools.

With independence in 1976, and the subsequent left-wing coup d'état in 1977, the status of Kreol Seselwa vastly improved. The elevation of Kreol Seselwa to a standardized official language was an important part of the regime's nation-building process, and a way of signalling a break from the colonial past. Under a short period in the early 1980s, Kreol Seselwa underwent an intensive language-planning process (Liddicoat, 2013, p.2) which involved the establishment of a standardized orthography, grammar and lexicon, and also the construction of a new curriculum and learning materials. In 1982, Kreol Seselwa was formally introduced in education as a subject from Primary 1-6 and the medium of

instruction from Primary 1-4 in state schools (see Fleischmann 2008, pp. 58-67 for further details of this process).

The elevation of Kreol Seselwa to an official language with a role in education was, however, not without complications. Large parts of the population saw the move as ideologically questionable – a political, rather than pedagogic, project which risked isolating Seychellois learners from the global community. In addition, many teachers argued that having Kreol Seselwa as medium of instruction and then switching to English in Primary 5 was challenging since children had to be ‘re-taught’ all basic concepts and terminology in subjects such as mathematics and the social and natural sciences (Deutschmann & Zelime, 2022).

Since the mid-nineties, the role of Kreol Seselwa in state education has gradually diminished. It is plausible that the lessened status granted to Kreol Seselwa in education and other spheres may have been influenced by the political transformations that occurred in the republic during the early nineties. In 1993, the advent of the ‘Third Republic’ marked Seychelles’ transition into a multi-party democracy with free elections. Consequently, Seychelles gradually shifted away from a predominantly centrally controlled planned economy, which heavily relied on aid from the former Soviet Union and its allies, towards a more open and liberal economic model. During this transition, prioritizing the consolidation of existing relationships and fostering new connections with influential global powers became increasingly important in the pursuit of integration into the global economic community (Laversuch, 2008. p.377). It is also conceivable that the governing party sought to distance itself from some of the more radical reforms implemented after it assumed power in 1977 to appeal to a broader segment of the electorate.

The introduction of Kreol Seselwa in education was perceived by some as one such radical reform. At the same time, Kreol Seselwa is now one of the official languages and an important part of the national identity. Politically, both these sentiments need to be considered when constructing language-in-education policy in Seychelles, and there appears to be an inherent dualism and discrepancy of interests between the global and local identity interests in language planning. This political balancing act unfortunately does not always take pedagogic considerations into account. This becomes evident when policy documents such as curricula are analysed in more detail. For example, the National Curriculum Framework (2013) and the subject-specific curricula documents associated with this document are highly contradictory (see Zelime & Deutschmann, 2016). The role and status of Kreol Seselwa is elevated in the rhetoric of the overall framework but downplayed in practical terms in the subject-specific curricula. Here it is important to note that all state-run schools offer International General Certificate of Secondary Education (IGCSEs) exams produced in Cambridge at the end of compulsory secondary school (year 11).

Whatever the reasons, from 1996 to date, the role of Kreol Seselwa in state education has become increasingly limited. It is now only used as medium of instruction during the first

two years of primary schooling and ceases to be a subject at school after Primary 6. English takes over as sole medium of instruction in all subjects except French from Primary 3. Furthermore, following a Ministry of Education recommendation in 2018, many schools implement English-only medium of instruction in mathematics and the sciences from Primary 1. Many teachers argue that Kreol Seselwa as a medium of instruction in school should be abandoned altogether (see Fleischmann, Schwarz & Nick, 2018; Zelime & Deutschmann, 2016).

The private school sector in Seychelles

The oldest international private school in Seychelles dates back to 1969, when the International School Seychelles on Mahé island was established. Initially this school only served non-Seychellois expatriates. During pre-independence, there were also two church-run elite schools offering O- and A-level education for Seychellois, namely The Seychelles College, a boy school opened in 1950 run by the Plöermel Brothers of Christian Instruction; and the Regina Mundi Convent Girl School, opened in January 1957 run by the Irish Sisters of Saint Joseph de Cluny ('Monument to honour...', 2016). These schools were remnants of the Catholic church-owned school system that was dismantled in the 1940s, but soon evolved into what essentially was a grammar school set-up. Both schools required tuition fees, but also offered bursary programs for students who could not afford the fees, but who qualified in the yearly national entrance examinations which determined admission to the secondary sections of both institutions. Regina Mundi and The Seychelles College were shut down in 1980 and 1982 respectively since it was deemed that the schools were elitist and did not comply with the education reforms and socialist policies at the time.

For many years no private school options were available in the country. In 1992, an amendment to the Educational Act (Act 5 of 1992) made it legal for Seychellois to attend private schools once again. The sector has grown steadily since then, and today there are six private schools – five EMI schools and one French medium school. None of these schools include Kreol Seselwa in their curricula¹ and many have strict English-only policies, even during breaks. Based on student data from the schools' homepage information, there are approximately 2700 students attending private schools in Seychelles. This constitutes approximately 15.5% of the national student population, which was approximately 17,500 in 2022 (The World Bank, 2023).

The fees in these private schools range from SCR (Seychelles Rupee) 60,000-100,000 per annum, depending on school and level, which translates into a monthly cost of SCR 5,000-8,500. This outlay is probably beyond the means of most of the average households in

¹ Note, however, that one of the smaller schools is currently developing extracurricular programs that involve local culture and language.

Seychelles, where 83% have a monthly income of less than SCR 25,000, and almost 60% have monthly incomes of less than SCR 15,000. Realistically speaking, it is really only the top 17% of the income bands that can afford to send their children to private school given that: a) the general cost of living in the Seychelles is very high; b) many families have more than one child, and c) there are many single parent families in the Seychelles – only 44% of children live with both of their parents (data from National Bureau of Statistics, 2024). In summary, the private school sector constitutes an important part of the Seychelles school ecology, especially since this is where many of the socio-economically privileged and influential citizens send their children to be educated.

Method

The results in this study are based on survey data collected via an online survey (SurveyMonkey) during 2023 from five of the six private schools in the Seychelles. A request to distribute the survey, together with an explanatory text on the aims of the study, was sent to the headteachers of all six private schools. Five EMI schools responded, and the link was subsequently distributed via the schools' parent group channels (e-mail lists and/or WhatsApp groups). The data thus represents language ideologies from parents who have sent their children to EMI schools only (i.e. the French medium of instruction school is not included in this study). Given the small size of Seychelles and that the number of respondents from each of the schools could potentially reveal their identities, the respondent data was analysed in bulk.

Pre-primary parents' responses were included in the analyses as these were deemed to still be representative of the group as a whole – pre-primary pupils will, after all, move on to become primary school pupils soon. Also, note that expatriate respondents, who constituted 22% of the respondent group, were included in the results. This group is, however, analysed separately.

Data on the parents' profession are based on an open-ended question on profession which was answered by 163 respondents. The following professional groupings emerged: managers and directors; self-employed, entrepreneurs and businessmen/women; educator workers, such as secondary school teachers, head teachers and university staff; skilled professionals, for example, engineers, marine biologists, pilots, psychologists etc.; workers in the financial and legal sector, such as bankers, accountants, auditors and lawyers. Furthermore, there were four minor professional categories: hotel and tourism workers (4%); Civil servants (4%); housewives (1%); and 'other' (1%). Noteworthy here was the relatively small number of parents employed within the tourism sector, which is the biggest employment sector in the Seychelles.

In sum, it was clear that the respondent group generally can be described as belonging to the category 'high socio-economic status'. A summary of the respondent metadata is given

below in Table 1. Notable here is the fact that a majority of the respondents were women which may have skewed the results. We have, however, not included gender as a variable in our analysis since we are primarily interested in the language habits and ideologies of the family as a whole.

Table 1: Respondent meta-data

Respondent Data (Total of 176 respondents)					
Gender	Mother			Father	
	144 (82%)			32 (18%)	
Age	>25	26-35	36-45	46-55	<56
	5	52	88	24	7
Resident status	Seychellois			Expatriates	
	137 (78%)			39 (22%)	
Child's school level	Pre-primary		Primary	Secondary	
	39 (22%)		76 (43%)	61 (35%)	
Highest level of education (parents)	Upper Secondary	Professional program	Bachelor's level	Master's level	Doctorate
	12 (7%)	74 (42%)	45 (26%)	40 (23%)	5 (3%)
Most common professional categories	Managers	Self-employed	Education workers	Skilled professionals	Law and finance
	35 (22%)	32 (20%)	28 (17%)	27 (17%)	24 (15%)

Apart from information about the respondent, the questionnaire included three sections: 1. Language habits in the home, 2. Views on the importance of the three national languages in different modes (spoken and written) and style contexts (formal and informal), and 3. Opinions on the role of Kreol Seselwa in education. The questionnaire included various types of question formats: Open ended questions; Likert scale responses, where 1=totally disagree and 7=totally agree to various statements; Multiple choice responses with one or several options; and Ranking questions. Each question also included a comment section where respondents were able to complement/explain/expand their responses. The questionnaire also included a request for consent that the responses be included in the research database. The language used in the questionnaire was English, but it was explicitly stated that respondents could use any of the three national languages (English, French and Kreol Seselwa) in their responses. All comments and and free text answers were given in English.

Results

The results below are split into three sections reflecting the structure of the questionnaire: language habits in the home; relative importance of the national languages; and views on

the role of Kreol Seselwa in education. Note that respondents were free to add comments to their responses and these have been summarized after each dataset below. Note that all comments provided by respondents are quoted verbatim. Language inconsistencies are not corrected.

Language policies within the family

The results below refer to Seychelles nationals only (n=137), as it is the language habits of this group that are of interest to this study. Results are based on responses to multiple-choice questions and statement responses where the respondents could disagree or agree on a seven-point Likert scale (1 = disagree completely; 4 = neither agree nor disagree; 7 = agree completely).

The first question in this section referred to how respondents would describe their family's language identity. From the group, 59% chose *bilingual*, 37% *multilingual*, and a mere 3% (4 respondents) *monolingual*. Of these four respondents, three spoke English only at home, and one French. When asked what languages were spoken at home (note that respondents could choose several alternatives here), the vast majority chose English (91%) and Kreol Seselwa (85%). French was chosen by 13% of the respondents and the category 'other languages' was chosen by 9%. Languages listed included Tamil, German, Kiswahili, Italian, Serbian, Spanish and Afrikaans. Among this group relatively few chose Kreol Seselwa, and it seems that these respondents primarily constituted Seychellois married to expatriates, or Seychellois who had a home language different from the official languages (Tamil, a language spoken by approximately 1% of the population according to the National Census 2022, for example).

I also asked respondents to react to three statements that reflected the family language policy: (a) *At home, we encourage our child to speak whatever language he/she chooses*; (b) *At home, we do not encourage our child to speak Kreol Seselwa*; and (c) *Between ourselves as parents, we communicate in a different language than with our children*. The average response to statement (a) was one of overall agreement (weighted average = 5.49), while respondents generally disagreed with statement (b) (weighted average 2.27). There were somewhat mixed responses to statement (c) (weighted average 3.15). A more detailed summary of how responses were distributed is given below in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Family language policies

Based on the distribution of the answers to these statements it seems that a large majority of parents encourage children to speak whatever language they choose and that there are only a few families that actively discourage the use of Kreol Seselwa at home. There does, however, seem to be quite a few cases where parents' language habits between themselves do not quite correspond to how they communicate with their children.

About 25% of respondents chose to comment on their responses. Based on these comments a more nuanced and complex picture of family language policy in the Seychelles emerges. Many parents emphasized the importance of Kreol Seselwa for their national identity, thereby motivating its use at home.

Seychelles Creole is part of our culture and heritage. I believe we should teach and encourage our children to learn and speak it freely in order to help them develop their identity.

Creole is our mother tongue, he needs to use it.

Creole is integral to our identity as Seychellois and to our culture, and we do not want our child to grow up not knowing how to speak it.

He needs to be able to speak to his grandparents!

Many respondents noted that although they as parents encourage the use of Kreol Seselwa at home, their children prefer to speak English. The main reason given for this was that the children speak English at school.

Our children are free to communicate in whichever language they prefer, but English is their main form of communication at school and they bring this home.

We do not discourage our children from speaking creole but we do encourage them to speak English too as they go to an English speaking school. However they are free to speak creole whenever they want. But they seem to have become more accustomed to speaking English at school and it is becoming more natural for them to speak English at home.

We would love for our children to know creole fluently. But because of English speaking schools we felt best to speak English with them and have them learn that first. But we would love for them to speak creole.

I started speaking only Creole to the child when a baby, but after starting pre school she chose to speak English. I switch between English & creole when speaking to the child.

Indeed, many parents seem rather split in their language approaches. They mainly speak English to their children, but almost seem to express regret for this.

They are encouraged to speak Creole but are shy to do so as they are not fluent. They would usually answer in English when spoken to in Creole, if they have understood it. English has been the medium of communication with them from birth.

It is not done on purpose. We speak English to the children most time because that's what they know best. We do speak creole with each other (my husband).

We try to teach him creole in between. But since he doesn't know most of the words he prefers English.

Many parents express clearer 50:50 approaches to English and Kreol Seselwa.

We began with English at a young age but now encourage both.

To mother - Mainly creole and English To father.

Our child speaks both, at his own choice.

A few comments propagate a strict English-only family policy often motivated by a denigration of Kreol Seselwa.

We communicate with him in English only

It's the child's education process not ours, hence we should not prejudice the child's ability to succeed in life by imposing a language on her that is her maternal tongue which, unfortunately,

has only 4000 words and therefore cannot do science, cannot do algebra, that you cannot discuss world affairs with, that loses the value of Plato, Aristotle and Socrates in translation.

Creole is a back kitchen language [...] we must be realistic, it has little to no external value unless one will go work for the Red Cross in Haiti.

A range of views of what is central to language also emerges. Some emphasize the importance of each language as distinct systems, while others put more emphasis on communication and feeling secure.

The child is free to choose to speak either English or Creole. But continuously reminded not to mix both.

I feel that most times my children express themselves in ways they feel comfortable. I encourage self development in any language. I find it stimulating for the brain for my children as well as for me.

It all depends on the situation and context. Sometimes, to express funny notes and ideas we choose the language that feels funny when to say whatever we want to say.

We speak Creolenglish.

Finally, French was only mentioned in two of the 99 comments in this section.

Sometimes French.

Creole and English... French.

In summary, it appears that most private school Seychellois homes are bilingual or multilingual, that a majority of homes allow children to speak the language/s they feel most comfortable with, and that Kreol Seselwa is not actively discouraged. It does seem, however, that many parents prioritise English in their family language policy, even if this is done somewhat reluctantly. One reason may be that children grow accustomed to English at school. It is also apparent that French plays a minor role in most homes.

Views on the relative importance of the three national languages

The results in the first part of this section are based on the responses to six statements where the respondents could disagree or agree on a seven-point Likert scale (1 = disagree completely; 4 = neither agree nor disagree; 7 = agree completely).

Figure 2: Views of the importance of the languages in different modes

As Figure 2 shows, English was considered most important by a majority of the respondents, both in written and oral contexts. The opinions of expatriates and Seychellois did not differ markedly on this point. Also obvious from the results is the importance given by both groups to the oral function of Kreol Seselwa. Both groups see Kreol Seselwa as more important than French in this mode. Writing Kreol Seselwa seems to be regarded as less important, and here both groups attach the least importance to Kreol Seselwa in this mode (even less than French, which also receives rather modest scores).

When separating formal and informal contexts, a more complex picture emerges (see Table 2 below). Note that the results here are based on ranking responses whereby respondents were invited to rank the three national languages in order of importance (1 = most important; 3 = least important) in different modes (written/spoken) and formality contexts (formal/informal). There was also an option to choose 'equally important'.

Table 2: Ranking of importance of languages, formal and informal – Seychellois and expatriate respondents

Rank of Importance	English	KS	French	Equally
In informal oral contexts	1.68* (1.44)**	1.58 (1.97)	2.88	9*** (3)
In formal oral contexts	1.27 (1.06)	2.38 (2.52)	2.46 (2.48)	9 (4)
In informal written contexts	1.34 (1.34)	2.29 (2.18)	2.58 (2.68)	14 (5)
In formal written contexts	1.21 (1.10)	2.59 (2.55)	2.35 (2.41)	12 (3)

* The average rank values were calculated by adding up all rank values (1,2 or 3) and dividing by the number of responses. Low values (1 minimum) represent high rankings and high values (3 maximum) represent low rankings.
 ** Numbers in brackets represent the expatriate results. Also note that bold represents the highest ranking.
 *** Figures under ‘equally’ represent the number of respondents who answered that they deemed languages to be equally important.

In summary, English was deemed to be the most important language in Seychelles in most of the contexts, and by both groups (with the exception of informal spoken contexts, see below). Kreol Seselwa was generally ranked as the second most important language, except in formal written communication. French was deemed to be the least important language except in formal written contexts, and by expatriates in formal spoken contexts. The opinions of the Seychellois and expatriate groups did not differ markedly, but there was a general tendency for expatriates to rank English slightly higher than the Seychellois group in all categories.

In informal contexts, many of the Seychellois respondents saw Kreol Seselwa as the most important language (63), which was a higher number than those who deemed English to be most important (42). The overall ranking score of Kreol Seselwa was, however, slightly reduced due to the fact that opinions were somewhat polarized; a relatively large number of Seychellois respondents (16) ranked it as the least important spoken language in informal contexts, which can arguably be seen as ideological statements, rather than a reflection of reality. Regardless, it still seems to be the case that most of the Seychellois parents in this study regard Kreol Seselwa to be the most important spoken language in everyday communication. Expatriate parents, though ranking English as the most important oral informal language, still acknowledged the importance of Kreol Seselwa in these contexts, ranking it much higher than French.

Again, after each question, the respondents were invited to comment freely, and approximately 10% did so. These comments are summarized below. In the comments referring to **oral contexts**, two themes emerged with reference to Kreol Seselwa. Firstly, a

majority of the respondents made the point that it is an important everyday language that most people use

Most people use creole in everyday life.

There were also several comments that pointed to the importance of Kreol Seselwa as part of the national identity.

This is our mother language. We cannot be born and live in Seychelles and not know how to communicate orally in creole.

Three main themes emerged from the comments related to the importance of English in oral modes. Firstly, many pointed to the importance of English in professional and administrative contexts.

You need English to conduct your everyday job. Especially those working in offices.

Secondly, the importance of English as a global language was emphasized. Such comments included travel but also English as a means of communicating with tourists.

English is one of the top languages spoken in the World so it is extremely important from a global perspective. We want our child to be ready for the World not just Seychelles.

We have to know how to communicate as we depend heavily on tourism.

Finally, many referred to the importance of English in education.

Apart from French and creole, all other subjects are taught in English in the government schools. So both understanding and speaking English are important. More than that, creole is not allowed in private schools.

There were fewer comments that made reference to French in oral contexts. Two main themes emerged. Firstly, there were comments that simply stated that knowing any language is a good thing.

One can never know too many languages.

Secondly, the importance of French in the tourism sector was mentioned.

I believe that the French language is becoming less important in local society. French is very useful in the tourism sector, however, as a large proportion of tourists are French speaking. In this respect, it is an important business language to the most important Seychelles economic contributor.

In the comments referring to **written contexts**, two main themes emerged with reference to Kreol Seselwa. Firstly, many comments simply emphasized that it is unimportant.

To my knowledge and experience in all situations where I have had to write something for professional use it is done so in English. Most services are provided for in English but some do also provide the creole version.

There were, however, a few comments that made reference to national language policies when commenting on the role of Kreol Seselwa as a written medium.

In the Seychelles one is allowed to use any of the national languages. Lots of information is in written creole and in the government schools, creole is taught as a subject.

The themes in the comments referring to written English were very similar to those that were mentioned under the oral contexts, i.e. the importance of English as an administrative and professional language, its value in global communication, and its benefits in educational contexts. There were a few disparate comments that referred to the importance of French. For example, one respondent referred to language policies and made the point that it is an official language.

It is after all one of our national languages and a plus as it is closely related to Creole.

Finally, one respondent pointed to the colonial past when discussing the relatively minor role that French plays in the Seychelles.

The politics of Francophonie have been defeated badly in seychelles because of the history of slavery and economic dominance of French families.

In summary, the written comments corroborate the quantitative data whereby English is seen as being of major importance in formal and written communication, while Kreol Seselwa is important as an everyday oral language. French seems to be regarded as a language of minor importance in most contexts.

Views on the role of Kreol Seselwa in education

The results below are based on responses to a multiple-choice question where respondents were asked to tick the statements that best described their views on the role of Kreol Seselwa in education. They could tick any number of statements and were also encouraged to comment on their answers. The results are summarized in Figure 3 below. Note that we have separated Seychellois (n=137) and expatriate (n=39) responses.

Figure 3. Views on various statements on the role of Kreol Seselwa in education

Interestingly, only a small minority of Seychellois and expatriate parents agree with the current language policies of the EMI private schools, i.e. that Kreol Seselwa has no role in education at all, and that it should not be used in school, even during breaks. Only about 4-5% of parents agreed with the latter policy. A majority of parents from both groups thought that Kreol Seselwa should be taught as a home language for Seychellois, and that it should be used in non-academic contexts, as well as a support language. Furthermore, a relatively large minority, about 42% wanted Kreol Seselwa to be taught as a subject in primary school, and many parents, especially expatriates (42%) thought that it should be a subject throughout the secondary curriculum.

The comments largely mirrored overall positive attitudes towards the potential role of Kreol Seselwa in education, and many parents were of the opinion that its role should be increased. Many expressed wishes for it to be introduced as a subject.

We would also appreciate having Creole classes as well...

I think it's very important for a child to learn their native language.

I believe it is important some basic of the mother tongue is taught, as a subject not as a mode of teaching.

Would be good for the students to learn the basic of creole at least in primary private school. Just like in public school.

One should be able to understand, write and communicate its own mother tongue. It is the teaching curriculum which should be reviewed.

I would really like Creole studies to be available to students and for expatriate teachers too, to give them an understanding of the culture in Seychelles, and help them to interact with students in a more informal manner outside of academic subjects.

Others emphasized its potential as a support language and even as a medium of instruction.

The mother tongue can be used to further the clarification. So it is useful in pedagogy, alongside the language used for assessment.

It can be used to build or elaborate on a certain concept being taught just as a means of explanation maybe, for those who feel more comfortable with creole. But the main instructive language should be English.

Many educational studies have shown that teaching through the mother tongue is largely more effective.

There were also a few largely negative comments expressing monolingual, English-only views.

Don't waste my child's life.

Do not prejudice my children's future with Creole.

I believe all subject should be taught using english as language as its most used world wide.

To summarize, it seems that the majority of parents would like to see reforms to the current language policies in relation to the role of Kreol Seselwa in private schools. Many would like to see it taught as a home language, and others would like to see it introduced as a subject in primary and secondary school. Only a very small minority reacted positively to the current English-only policies.

Discussion

It is apparent that the results from this study mirror similar studies on parent attitudes conducted in recent years (Al-Qahtani & Al Zumor, 2016; Bailey, 2021; Paulsrud & Cunningham, forthcoming). On the one hand, parents refer positively to the linguistic capital afforded by English in terms of prestige and access to global education and the job market (cf. MacKenzie, 2010). In this study, many also refer to the local affordances of English – in tourism and in professional contexts. This linguistic capital also spills over in the family language policies, where many parents testify to speaking English with their children to prepare them for school and life in general.

On the other hand, with reference to Kreol Seselwa, many mention the importance of the language as a marker of social identity and the fact that it is the most common language used in everyday communication. Here several comments corroborate findings from other studies, i.e. that many parents lament the loss of the language capital of the local language that EMI schooling entails. Interestingly, many parents describe how, despite efforts to promote Kreol Seselwa in the family, children prefer to communicate in English at home because they have been influenced by the linguistic environment at school. Concerns expressed include identity loss and that children become cut off from their older relatives and society as a whole. Very similar issues were raised in Al-Qahtani & Al Zumor's (2016) and Bailey's (2021) studies, and these findings in turn validate the potential dangers of EMI pointed out by Baker (2011) (i.e. loss of cultural and/or ethnic identity). It appears that issues such as these are of real concern to the Seychellois parents in this study, who generally lean towards 'English AND local language' rather than 'English-only' policies. Interestingly, expatriate parents also see the value of their children learning Kreol Seselwa. Arguably, the importance of acculturation, i.e. the will to incorporate into the prevalent culture by participating in aspects of the culture such as language, may have been underestimated among this group in Seychelles.

As regards the potential role of Kreol Seselwa in education it is notable that a large majority want to see it taught as a 'home language'. This would enable Seychellois children in the private sector to develop their writing proficiency and to use the language in more complex discursive contexts. There are also many who would like to see it become a regular part of the curriculum, both at primary and secondary levels. It is noteworthy that only 5% believe that it should not be used during breaks, and a mere 13% believe that Kreol Seselwa should have no role in education. These practices are in fact current language policies in four of the five of the schools investigated, which seems to suggest that a majority of parents are open to language policy reforms that give Kreol Seselwa a more prominent role in the system.

There is, however, a very vocal minority who are totally against the promotion of Kreol Seselwa. Some of the arguments used against its use are circular – 'Kreol Seselwa should not be promoted because it is not used in private schools', while other statements are

downright false: Kreol Seselwa has 22,000 dictionary entries in the latest dictionary, and not 4,000 as suggested by one respondent.

Both arguments, however, illustrate an important point. Language-in-education policy is a balancing act where either recessive or expansive cycles can be the outcome. On the one hand, the lack of use of a language in more formal domains gives further fuel to those that claim that local languages, such as Kreol Seselwa, are unfit for education and official purposes, resulting in further limitations to the domains where they are used, which in turn reinforces negative attitudes. On the other hand, expanded efforts in promoting languages such as Kreol Seselwa could mean that they grow in status and become acknowledged, alongside English, as fit for use in education and perhaps even in official domains such as administration and business, thereby motivating their promotion in education to higher levels, which in turn raises their status.

One important aspect of such language status promotion is how private schools relate to local languages in their language policies. Based on the results of this study, there is one particularly strong argument for giving Kreol Seselwa a more prominent role in private EMI schools: parents (Seychellois and expatriates alike) seem to crave it! There are of course many other more pedagogically motivated arguments for using Kreol Seselwa alongside English in education.

Kreol Seselwa would open up a closer integration of local context and culture in everyday learning activities, and a subject orientation which included language, history and culture with a national and *international* focus (cf. Creole Studies) could also lead to a better understanding of local history and culture, and how this is connected to creole cultures internationally. This 'glocal' understanding of the national linguistic and cultural identity is arguably important knowledge for a nation that is dependent on tourism. As an extension of this idea, I would argue that the establishment of *Creole Studies* in schools in the Seychelles could, and should, include the elevation of the subject to an examinable subject under the IGCSE system; the Cambridge IGCSE subject portfolio contains numerous African language subjects such as IsiZulu, Swahili and Setswana. Even though it would arguably be challenging to examine specific aspects of language proficiency under such a scheme given the diversity of creole languages and what we have to assume is a limited linguistic competence of small creole languages such as Kreol Seselwa in Cambridge, Creole Studies could be structured in such a way that it consisted of a core content of relevance to numerous creole contexts (general linguistics, history and culture). The specific language proficiency aspects could then be examined locally in different national contexts.

Conclusion

In this paper, I have attempted to examine language ideologies and language habits of families whose children attend private schools in Seychelles. I have also been interested in finding out what the views of parents are concerning the role of Kreol Seselwa in education. The ambition has been to test the hypothesis that private school parents generally are sceptical to the role of Kreol Seselwa and even discourage their children from using it in the home environment.

Although, as expected, we find a range of language habits and views among our respondents, we can, based on the overall patterns found in the data, dismiss the hypothesis that private school parents are generally negative towards Kreol Seselwa in Seychelles. Instead, a more complex picture emerges where parents are split between prioritizing the linguistic economic and global capital afforded by English, and the cultural and identity capital afforded by Kreol Seselwa. The data clearly show that parents fully recognize the importance of English in professional and formal contexts. At the same time, the importance of Kreol Seselwa in defining individual and national identity, and the role of the language as primary spoken medium in the Seychelles, are emphasized.

Many comments also reveal that this balancing act becomes even more complex when English-only policies of private schools lead children to acquire different linguistic identities and habits than their parents and the surrounding community. There is a risk that these children become linguistically and culturally isolated, while parents at the same time feel that this is legitimate since they are merely trying to do what is best for their children. This is arguably not a sustainable situation given that schools want to work towards social equity and counteract elite-closure (cf. U.N Sustainable Development Goal 4, United Nations, 2015). The opinions of the parents clearly show that Kreol Seselwa should have a role in education, even in private schools.

In conclusion, this study recommends an approach that prioritizes both English AND Kreol Seselwa in the private school curricula. Such an approach would still recognize the global importance of English, while at the same acknowledging and preserving students' and the nation's cultural and linguistic heritage. A way forward could be the establishing of Creole Studies throughout the system and ultimately also at university level. This could help in elevating Kreol Seselwa academically, not only locally but also from an international global perspective – a 'glocal' solution, so to say.

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